

The Impact of Educational Leadership Style on Instructors' Retention Rate in Higher Education Institutions

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ABSTRACT

This study explored how different leadership styles influenced the decision of instructors to stay at Davao de Oro State College. Faculty turnover had become a growing concern for the institution, raising questions about what leadership approaches might encourage long-term commitment among educators. Guided by Bass's Transformational Leadership Theory, the research focused on three leadership styles: transformational, transactional, and instructional. Using a quantitative, descriptive-correlational ex post facto design, the researcher gathered data from 28 instructors who had served for at least five years across four campuses. Survey tools adapted from previous studies helped capture how faculty perceived the leadership behaviors of their academic heads. The findings showed that while transformational leadership was not commonly observed, it still had a positive connection to instructor retention. Transactional leadership had a moderate influence, but instructional leadership stood out with the strongest correlation, especially because of its emphasis on professional growth and direct support for teachers. The study concluded that leadership plays a vital role in shaping a work environment where instructors feel valued and motivated to stay. Strengthening instructional and transformational leadership practices may therefore help reduce turnover and build a more stable academic community.

Keywords: education, teaching, leadership

INTRODUCTION

Effective educational leadership in higher education relies on various performance roles. This involves various aspects, including administration, instruction, guidance, leadership of faculty, as well as the organization and assessment of educational activities. Furthermore, numerous factors play a role in the contentment and retention of faculty members in higher education. Leaders in higher education must understand the institution's culture. Measures that enhance faculty satisfaction contribute to a positive professional atmosphere and support faculty retention. When developing and executing policies and establishing goals, leadership practices should consider an educator's personal and academic experiences. According to Petersen and O'Reilly (2020), good educational leadership practices are essential for any educational institution to function and accomplish its institutional objectives and goals. The retention of faculty in higher education is connected to numerous factors significantly shaped by the institution's leadership and culture. A supportive atmosphere acknowledging faculty concerns, values, and perspectives leads to greater satisfaction and motivation among faculty members. Leaders in higher education need to assess ways to improve their organizational leadership.

Additionally, research conducted by Welbeck et al. (2024) in China found that transformational leadership significantly enhances employee performance, while transactional leadership positively influences employee satisfaction. Consequently, in Chinese public high schools, transformational leadership is more effective in achieving performance targets, whereas transactional leadership is better suited for fostering employee satisfaction. Furthermore, in one of the private academic institutions in Olongapo City, Philippines, a study conducted by Mondejar and Asio (2022) on the educational leadership practices, in which the indicators are the Human Resource Management (HRM) practices and job satisfaction. The study revealed a highly significant value of good educational leadership style when it comes to the retention rate of teachers.

In the context of Davao de Oro State College, where the researcher is currently teaching, the retention rate of instructors is undeniably a challenge for the administration, faculty members, and students, as it affects the delivery of quality educational services to all stakeholders. The researcher was inspired to conduct this endeavor to determine the impact of educational leadership styles on the retention rate of instructors in higher education institutions. As observed, every year in the school where the researcher is currently employed, the turnover of teachers is quite alarming, and the reasons or causes of these fast turnovers of college teachers are unknown to many. This has been experienced every year or even at the end of the semester. Based on the records from human resource office, from 2021 there is a 2.5% turn-over rate, in 2022, there is 3.67%, in 2023 there is 6.95%, and in 2024 it is 14.90%, based on the given data, there is an increased of percentage rate when it comes to the faculty separation. This scenario triggers the researcher to conduct a study to determine if one of the causes of the turnover of college instructors is the leadership style of the school administrators. Therefore, there is a need to conduct this study, the results of which could be of help to the school administrators to improve how they lead and manage the school.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the effect of educational leadership style or instructors' retention rate. Specifically, it sought to provide answer to the following questions:

1. What is the level of the educational leadership style of academic leaders in terms of:
 - 1.1 transactional leadership;
 - 1.2 transformational leadership; and
 - 1.3 instructional leadership?
2. What is the extent of the retention rate of teachers?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of transactional leadership style and the retention rate of instructors in the institution?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of transformational leadership and the retention rate of teachers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of instructional leadership and the retention rate of teachers?

Null Hypotheses

With the problems in this study, the hypotheses below are formulated:

There is no significant relationship between the transactional leadership style and the retention rate of teachers.

There is no significant relationship between the transformational leadership style and the retention rate of teachers.

There is no significant relationship between the instructional leadership style and the retention rate of teachers.

Scope and Delimitations

This study was focused on the impact of educational leadership style on the instructors' retention rate of higher education institutions, specifically the Davao de Oro State College, with an inclusion of all campuses comprising New Bataan, Montevista, Maragusan, and Compostela/Main Campuses from academic year 2021-2025. The study's data were limited to all teachers whose length of service is five years or more in the college. The data collected on the retention rate were taken from 2021 to 2024. Moreover, the researcher only focused on the educational leadership styles, such as transactional, transformational, and instructional leadership, and the extent of the educational leadership styles of academic leaders related to the retention rate of instructors in the institution.

Literature Review

Leadership Styles. The effectiveness of leadership relies on the various styles of leaders. It extends beyond just management. Leaders are considered effective when they can embrace change, make inclusive decisions, keep

communication channels open, and guide others to achieve their objectives. As Bass and Bass (2009) described, effective leadership evolves through an ongoing journey of personal reflection, learning, training, and gaining pertinent experiences. Jenkins (2013) emphasized that the foundation of effective leadership lies in having a robust character and a selfless commitment to an organization. Different leadership styles can be found in the empirical literature. Transformational and transactional leadership styles are commonly recognized approaches that shape the leadership philosophy employed in professional settings (Gandolfi and Stone, 2018). Based on the systematic review by Specchia et al. (2021), leadership styles play a crucial role in influencing employee satisfaction while executing effective policies for daily operations. Fries et al. (2021) suggested that leadership styles are rooted in innate and learned behaviors exhibited by individuals, which prove effective in professional settings. Nevertheless, irrespective of the definition, the selected style is usually deemed suitable only within the organization's context, area of expertise, and leadership traits (Fries et al., 2021; Gandolfi & Stone, 2018; Specchia et al., 2021).

An educational leader should skillfully guide and assist staff and faculty within academic environments (McCaffery, 2018). Gonaim (2019) conducted a review on leadership in higher education institutions in Saudi Arabia, utilizing interviews with 14 department chairs. Research indicated that a modest method of leading staff played a significant role in fostering acceptance and nurturing positive interactions between followers and leaders. Like Gonaim (2019), Vilkinas et al. (2020) utilized survey data from 439 managers about follower and leader relationship dynamics. Vilkinas et al. (2020) discovered that positive motivators enhanced the relationships between employees and leaders. McCaffery (2018) suggested that the way employees perceive leaders is the primary factor that shapes the value of those leaders. When examining leadership within a broader framework, the approaches and techniques employed by leaders are frequently understood in terms of their followers' perceptions (Gonaim, 2019; McCaffery, 2018; Vilkinas et al., 2020). In higher education, effective leadership styles should be customized to meet stakeholders' requirements, including faculty, staff, and students (Carvalho et al., 2022; Farrukh et al., 2019). Carvalho et al. (2022) suggested that when transformational leadership is used in learning communities, it inspires staff and faculty to address the needs of students. Farrukh et al. (2019), like Carvalho et al. (2022), contended that the leadership of higher education institutions necessitates a leader who employs transformational leadership to motivate followers towards achieving educational objectives. In an academic setting, the particular leadership approach can greatly advantage the various stakeholders within the institution (Carvalho et al., 2022; Farrukh et al., 2019).

Transformational Leadership. As stated by Northouse (2019), transformational and transactional leadership exist on separate continua; however, Bass focused more on the needs of the followers and introduced a comprehensive model of transformational leadership that integrated both transformational and transactional leadership along a unified continuum. By motivating followers to seek and achieve outstanding performance, transformational leadership resulted in significantly high job and organizational satisfaction levels among followers (Banks et al., 2016). Transformational leadership focuses on the idea that leaders should inspire followers to strive for more than just achieving goals and reaching self-actualization (Daniels, Hondgehem, & Dochy, 2019). This concept is intricate as it pertains to self-efficacy and leadership, where transformational leadership has been pivotal in driving educational change and leadership (Anderson, 2017; Hesbol, 2019; Wirawan et al., 2019). Furthermore, it integrates and expands upon the goals of the individuals within an organization, forming an organizational community (Carleton et al., 2018). As a result, the organization's objectives become easier to achieve when leaders and followers engage in collaborative and collective efforts. Transformational leadership is currently the favored leadership approach in many schools (Anderson, 2017). The shared teamwork fostered by transformational leadership is essential for educational leaders to improve overall school performance (Anderson, 2017). Transformational leadership refers to the capacity to evolve an organization, enabling it to improve significantly (Carleton et al., 2018). Transformational leadership depends on the leader's capability to foster new leadership from every level of followers (Curtis, 2017).

Similarly, transformational leadership has a positive relationship with different elements of educational leadership, including team performance, job satisfaction, and organizational learning (Thomas et al., 2020; Waruwu et al., 2020). Furthermore, transformational leadership promotes the well-being of both the physical and mental health of leaders (Schermuly & Meyer, 2020). Given the strong support for the crucial role of transformational leadership in education, it underscores the importance of examining the connection between transformational leadership and leaders' self-efficacy and emotional intelligence. Transformational leaders can inspire employees to exceed performance expectations and encourage them to feel a strong sense of satisfaction and commitment to their team and the organization (Bass & Riggio, 2006; Choi et al., 2016). Leaders displaying a transformational

leadership approach motivate and inspire their team members, prioritize their employees' needs, and align their workers' goals and values with those of the organization (Andersen et al., 2018). Leaders who prioritize meeting the essential needs of their employees and recognizing their greater ambitions inspire workers to produce innovative and creative solutions that drive positive change in the workplace. Transformational leadership enhances employee motivation, raises morale, and improves performance at work while cultivating a commitment to the organization among staff members. As a result, transformational leadership is a constructive approach to keeping employees engaged and inspiring workers in lower-paying positions.

Transformational leaders promote their team members' individual development and advancement by motivating and enhancing their comprehension. This leadership style encourages significant and advantageous transformations among followers, with leaders acting as role models who demonstrate intellectual engagement and concern for their team (Holstad et al., 2014; Katou, 2015). Leaders prioritize enhancing their employees' development and utilize their strengths to encourage and uplift them. Leaders prioritize improving their employees' development and utilize their strengths to encourage and uplift them. Unlike other leadership approaches, transformational leaders serve as supporters, advisors, mentors, motivators, inspirers, attentive listeners, and coaches to share and develop the vision of their team members (Jyoti & Bhau, 2015; Mathew & Gupta, 2015). Leaders strive to establish an improved workplace for the employees of the organization. Researchers studying transformational leadership, Henker et al. (2015), claimed that transformational leadership plays a vital role in promoting creative engagement in the workplace, especially when trying new methods without the apprehension of failing.

Employees are urged to get involved in making decisions at work to contribute fresh ideas that enhance their skills. Leaders encouraging employee creativity inspire their team to reach constructive results (Dhar, 2015; Schmidt & Pohler, 2015; Qu et al., 2015). Furthermore, the transformational initiative is a crucial precursor to establishing the confidence or resilience needed to succeed when facing significant challenges (Gillet & Vandenberghe, 2014). Leaders who employ transformational leadership attain positive outcomes by encouraging, inspiring, and assisting employees in expressing their ideas. Transformational leadership managers create a genuine feeling of a leader who encourages staff to achieve and surpass their typical performance levels and individual aspirations. This leadership style was the most prominent during the 2010s for fostering positive organizational change.

Transformational leaders foster trust, admiration, reliability, and respect among their employees. They motivate their followers to embrace open-mindedness and to promote a culture of trust and collaboration within the team (Boies et al., 2015). Transformational leadership positively impacts employee satisfaction, productivity, performance, and effectiveness (Andersen et al., 2017; Belias & Koustelios, 2014). As a result, researchers concluded that organizations must have strong leaders who motivate employees to go beyond their expectations, foster a positive culture, and inspire their team members to become transformational leaders in their own right. Zwingmann et al. (2014) noted that a key characteristic of transformational leaders is their ability to communicate a vision to their followers that highlights the organization's elevated core needs and objectives. Moreover, transformational leadership signifies a reciprocal relationship wherein leaders and followers impact one another and derive mutual benefits (Kuhnert & Lewis, 1987). Transformational leaders improve how employees view and anticipate the organization while striving towards a shared objective that impacts the company's financial performance. According to Cetin and Kinik (2015), the dynamics of transformational leadership consist of followers (a) personally connecting with a leader, (b) sharing a common vision for the future, (c) collaborating for the good of the group, (d) feeling valued and respected by their peers, and (e) possessing a distinct sense of purpose. Effective leadership should inspire employees by fostering a commitment to shared objectives and a collective vision; creativity should be promoted, and individual differences should be valued.

The four dimensions, commonly known as the four I's of transformational leadership, represent characteristics shown by a seasoned leader in a knowledge-driven economy focused on cultivating and overseeing intellectual assets in organizations (Ghasabeh et al., 2015). Fallah et al. (2014) characterized II as an emotional aspect of leadership, the charm that inspires followers and fosters trust and confidence between the leader and the employee. Employees are more motivated and efficient when they sense their contributions are recognized or valued, especially when leaders articulate their importance to the organization (White, 2014). Leaders serve as exemplars, showcasing particular ethical conduct as they set a standard through their actions (Kamal & Kamal, 2014; Cetin & Kinik, 2015). Additionally, displayed behavior may indicate strong moral and ethical standards (Sosik et al., 2014). Followers often seek to replicate the actions of their leaders (Caillier, 2014). Leaders who

demonstrate effective behavior encourage their followers to cultivate trust, enhancing employees' appreciation and value, ultimately fostering stronger working relationships with their teams.

The Idealized Influence (II) consists of two components: attributional and behavioral. The II framework can also be divided into attributional and behavioral elements (Schweitzer, 2014). The attributional component relates to how subordinates view their leader (Northouse, 2013). For instance, the compelling leader guarantees team members will surmount obstacles (Rana et al., 2016). The behavioral aspect pertains to how followers perceive their leader's actions (Belias & Koustelios, 2014). For instance, employees might witness their supervisor navigating challenges (Northouse, 2013). The leader wants employees to view their leadership and interactions with others favorably. Individuals in leadership roles who display exemplary conduct impact how their employees view them, thereby improving the effectiveness and performance of their team. Inspirational motivation (IM) is another aspect of transformational leadership that fosters a sense of optimism and dedication. IM contemplates leaders who inspire their followers to embrace the collective organizational vision and to pursue elevated standards (Hoffmeister et al., 2014). Leaders clarify the group's expectations using straightforward language that all team members can grasp, minimizing complex topics, and promoting meaningful sacrifices (Mittal & Dhar, 2015). Leaders help establish priorities and a sense of purpose that are in harmony with their followers' interests and the organization's objectives (Cetin & Kinik, 2015). Leaders communicate the organization's goals to motivate employees to adopt the business vision. Employees recognize their part in the organization by pursuing this vision, which cultivates a feeling of being part of something significant and boosts team spirit and enthusiasm.

When employees grasp the company's overall vision, it can significantly impact the organization's success in reaching its objectives. According to Northouse (2015), leaders exhibiting impression management recognize followers' crucial role in the organization's future development. Elevating the vision allows employees to discover greater significance in their tasks, which may reduce turnover (Cetin & Kinik, 2015; Patton, 2015). Leaders utilized symbols and emotional appeals to capture the group's interest (Northouse, 2013). TLT leaders demonstrated a collaborative spirit to boost enthusiasm and motivation throughout the organization (Jiang et al., 2018). Employees can take on challenges, work towards the objectives, and surpass expectations (Hirschi & Valero, 2017). Additionally, leaders fostered a sense of camaraderie to achieve the organization's objectives. Moreover, leaders invigorated their followers through visionary and motivational approaches, encouraging them to embrace the organization's commitment to achieving future objectives. The employee believed they had a reason to come to work and meet high standards. The intellectual stimulation (IS) component involves transformational leaders sharing knowledge and motivating followers to broaden their thinking beyond their typical limits. In an environment free from the fear of reprimand, employees embraced innovative, sometimes contentious, methods and participated in problem-solving that fostered exceptional ideas. The leader encourages staff to employ their imagination and creativity when addressing organizational challenges (Bacha, 2014). Leaders motivate their team members to reassess issues and develop a fresh perspective on their thinking and problem-solving methods. By using IS, transformational leaders reevaluate essential beliefs (Cetin & Kinik, 2015). When workers apply their expertise and participate in problem-solving, it empowers them to generate ideas and make decisions, fostering creativity among their peers. Additionally, employees can acquire knowledge, advance, and evolve within the organization.

By providing individualized consideration (IC), a leader mentor aids, hears, and addresses the employee's needs. Leaders exhibiting interpersonal communication (IC) pay attention to and focus on the distinct needs of their followers, create an encouraging environment, and enable their supporters (Norman et al., 2015). Leaders view their subordinates as individuals instead of merely as part of a group, recognizing their unique needs and responding to them in an acceptable manner to each employee (Ghasabeh et al., 2015). Cetin and Kinik (2015) outlined the key characteristics of IC as the capability to acknowledge individual variations in strengths, weaknesses, preferences, and aversions. Leaders implemented IC by actively listening, delegating tasks to suitable team members, fostering open communication, and supporting personal growth (Chua & Murray, 2015). Ultimately, leaders who exhibit emotional intelligence nurture self-actualized employees through coaching, mentoring, and educating their team members (Northouse, 2013). Transformational leaders focus on the individual needs of their team members and create a supportive atmosphere. Each employee possesses distinct characteristics, strengths, and potential areas for growth; leaders act as coaches and mentors, guiding employees to overcome their weaknesses and become more valuable contributors. The leader is crucial in delegating tasks to employees that enhance morale and productivity.

Furthermore, transformational leaders are impactful figures who provide the necessary resources to enhance relationships between leaders and employees. According to Taylor et al. (2014), transformational leadership can enhance the connection between a leader and their subordinates by effectively communicating the organization's vision. When the organization's vision is expressed clearly, employees do not waste time determining which path to follow or become disengaged from that vision. A stronger connection between management and employees could increase the engagement of workers and foster awareness, which may motivate them to exceed their typical performance levels (Chiaburu et al., 2014). Transformational leaders can enhance employee performance by articulating the organization's vision and encouraging employees to participate in the company's growth. This cultivates high levels of commitment, trust, and motivation, ultimately resulting in greater organizational performance and efficiency. Transformational leaders who facilitate change among their employees can promote an optimistic perspective that increases motivation and support for the workforce. Similarly, transformational leaders who exhibit charismatic traits can inspire, motivate, and intellectually engage their employees (Afsar et al. 2014). Leaders encourage their employees to explore creative methods for accomplishing tasks and addressing challenges by sharing knowledge. These practices enable subordinates to reach their full potential and deliver exceptional performance levels (Pradhan & Pradhan, 2015). Transformational leaders prioritize their employees' best interests while fostering positive change to achieve significant goals through their charisma and commitment to high moral and ethical standards that motivate their teams (Dartey-Baah, 2015). Additionally, transformational leaders who serve as role models contribute to increased employee productivity (Irmal et al., 2015). Additionally, leaders who foster stronger connections with their employees cultivate an improved work environment that supports the organization's vision and objectives. This type of leadership also facilitates successful change management, with transformational leaders serving as change agents who drive organizational change and promote behaviors among employees focused on change (Kaur Bagga et al., 2022).

A transformational leader is an active leader who catalyzes change, enhances team members' awareness by prioritizing their shared advantages, and encourages the group to strive for outstanding objectives (Busari et al., 2020; Islam et al., 2021). Transformational leadership significantly affects how engaged employees are in facilitating organizational change (Hussain et al., 2021), and more effective transformational leadership results in more impactful organizational change (Ghasabeh, 2021; Odeh et al., 2021; Ratina et al., 2021). Furthermore, transformational leadership is regarded as the most advantageous and preferred style of leadership due to the leader's capacity to inspire and encourage employees to develop and strive toward a shared organizational vision (Reynolds, 2022). Leaders of this nature take the initiative and serve as catalysts for change; they enhance their subordinates' awareness by highlighting the shared advantages and inspire teams to reach outstanding objectives (Busari et al., 2020; Islam et al., 2021). For organizations and businesses to thrive, leaders must demonstrate a style that will encourage and energize employees to fulfill the organization's goals and attain the intended results (Baque et al., 2020). Consequently, businesses and organizations led by transformational leaders reach their intended goals and experience increased productivity, decreased employee turnover, improved returns on investment, greater job satisfaction, and reduced employee stress levels (Islami & Mulolli, 2020).

Transactional Leadership. Transactional leaders bring about change by gaining the compliance of their followers (Duemer, 2017). In contrast, transformational leaders motivate organizational change by fostering shared visions or objectives (Carleton, Barling, & Trivisonno, 2018). Duemer (2017) states that transactional leadership emphasizes conventional management practices and the upkeep of current relationships. Transactional leadership is a recognized approach in which a leader motivates followers to conform to their interests; followers are instructed to follow the leader's guidance without considering their thoughts and motivations (Duemer, 2017). This approach to leadership tackles swift organizational transformation by leaders aiming to gain the adherence of their followers via a method of conditional rewards and penalties (Barnett, 2018). Historically, a person or group in a position of power is recognized for trading something valuable in return for labor, influence, or information, often described as *quid pro quo* (Duemer, 2017). As a result, transactional leadership has been primarily regarded as a precursor to transformational leadership (Lee & Kuo, 2019; Sun et al., 2017).

Additionally, transactional leaders strongly emphasize maintaining hierarchical structures and compensation (Tyssen et al., 2014). Moreover, transactional leaders exhibit reactive behaviors, addressing issues once they occur, and are crucial in enhancing organizational performance (Birasnav, 2014). Transactional leaders instruct employees on what actions to take and anticipate that the worker will execute the tasks accordingly. Ultimately, employees look forward to receiving rewards in recognition of their performance. Transactional leaders employed a reactive strategy, utilizing positive and negative reinforcement to enhance employee performance. While punishment is not explicitly stated, it is implied that failing to complete tasks could result in disciplinary measures.

Max Weber's initial discussions of transactional leadership focus on positive and negative transactions, often called contingent rewards and management by exceptions (Bass & Bass, 2008; McCleskey, 2014). Contingent rewards enable leaders to communicate preferred goals and support expectations through tangible or psychological incentives (Bass & Bass, 2008; Khan, 2017). Potential material incentives may consist of cash bonuses, increases in salary, and both written and verbal acknowledgments or evaluations. Psychological incentives complement material rewards, incorporating elements like recognition, affirmative feedback, or constructive criticism (Bass & Bass, 2008). Incentives enable leaders to promote the accomplishment of goals or tasks by encouraging collaboration among followers based on rewards for appropriate behavior (Bass & Bass, 2008; Khan, 2017).

Relying exclusively on contingent rewards does not guarantee positive performance or commitment from followers. Management by exception serves as a corrective approach that allows leaders to monitor followers' errors or deviations and tackle issues through disciplinary measures, constructive criticism, or overt disapproval of follower actions (Bass & Bass, 2008; Khan, 2017). Leaders who consistently monitor misconduct and mistakes can regularly tackle poor performance among their followers. Yet, many leaders still tend toward passivity. Proactive leaders engage in both prevention and correction. In contrast, passive leaders usually avoid corrective measures unless problems arise (Bass & Bass, 2008; Khan, 2017). Additionally, Avci (2015) and Reid and Dold (2018) proposed that transactional leadership encompasses reciprocal situational exchanges between leaders and their followers, while Brinia and Papantoniou (2016) indicated that this approach is inherently managerial and depends less on the deliberate formation of interpersonal relationships. Transactional followers usually comply with their leaders by displaying acceptable behavior in hopes of obtaining a reward (Brinia & Papantoniou, 2016). The subordinates' satisfaction, involvement, and dedication levels correspond with intrinsic or extrinsic reward systems (Crews et al., 2019). The transactional leadership-followership dynamic theory suggests that particular actions can enhance conditions or achieve goals for all stakeholders involved (MacNeill et al., 2018). Even though there is voluntary cooperation among leaders and followers, transactional leadership is often seen as limited in its range because it depends on situational agreements that lack the greater purpose found in transformational leadership (Reid & Dold, 2018). Transactional leaders help define the roles and task expectations for employees motivated to put in the effort and achieve the desired outcomes. The explanation offers followers the reassurance they need to pursue their tasks and helps them recognize how meeting their needs can be achieved through their effective performance. This ensures that the intended result holds significant value for the follower, leading to a motivation to achieve that result.

Similarly, transactional leadership occurs when leaders and followers establish a relationship based on exchange to fulfill their self-interests (Avci, 2015). Transactional leaders direct and inspire followers towards achieving organizational objectives by clearly defining role expectations and task requirements, employing the management by exception philosophy to ensure employees remain aligned with the goals, and providing contingent rewards for those who complete the assigned tasks (Odetunde, 2013). Transactional leadership involves offering rewards based on performance to motivate employees to achieve organizational objectives and implementing corrective measures when those objectives are not realized (Avci, 2015). Transactional leaders' organizational objectives are paramount, and they leverage their positional authority to ensure that each employee prioritizes these objectives (Odetunde, 2013). This mutually advantageous connection fosters the self-interest of both the leader and the employee while ensuring they pursue the same goals. For example, a study conducted by Tremblay, Vandenberghe, and Doucet (2013) with 3,065 managers across 41 business units found a positive correlation between contingent rewards and employee satisfaction. Transactional leadership theory aids in understanding management and is significant because effective leadership strategies affect organizational success (Avci, 2015).

Instructional Leadership Style. Instructional leadership involves school leaders engaging directly in curriculum development, monitoring teacher effectiveness, and fostering a supportive educational atmosphere, all of which have been thoroughly studied concerning their impact on teacher retention. Therefore, effective instructional leadership fosters a positive school environment, boosts teacher job satisfaction, and reduces turnover rates. The role of instructional leadership is vital in improving student learning results by cultivating an atmosphere that encourages effective teaching strategies (Karadag, 2018). This leadership style focuses on enhancing organizational effectiveness and boosting student performance by establishing explicit, overarching goals for the school, guaranteeing that learning resources are accessible, overseeing and assessing teachers, and promoting professional development initiatives (Hallinger et al., 2020). In contrast to conventional leadership models that mainly concentrate on administrative duties or resource allocation, instructional leadership highlights the connection between school leaders and educators, giving precedence to instruction quality and classroom

practices' effectiveness (Tang et al., 2022). Through proactive involvement with teachers, instructional leaders cultivate a cooperative environment that improves teaching methods and supports professional development. This vibrant exchange between leaders and educators is crucial for ensuring that school policies and teaching practices are in harmony with the learning requirements of students. Instructional leadership is vital in enhancing multiple facets of teacher well-being and effectiveness. A significant advantage of this leadership approach is encouraging collaboration among teachers, which fosters knowledge exchange and peer support, ultimately resulting in more creative teaching strategies (Goddard et al., 2015; Liu & Hallinger, 2018). When educators collaborate within professional learning communities, they foster a collective responsibility for the success of students, which leads to enhanced instructional quality.

Additionally, instructional leadership is crucial in enhancing teacher job satisfaction by fostering a supportive workplace where educators feel appreciated and driven (Dutta & Sahney, 2022). When administrators set clear expectations, offer constructive feedback, and create avenues for professional development, educators are more inclined to feel satisfied in their roles and stay dedicated to their schools. This subsequently aids in lowering teacher turnover and improving institutional stability. An important element of instructional leadership is its impact on teacher engagement. Educators who feel they have robust leadership backing are more inclined to foster a stronger commitment to their roles and the institution's goals (Khan et al., 2023). When school leaders engage teachers in decision-making and recognize their input, educators develop a deeper connection to their jobs, promoting lasting commitment. Instructional leadership boosts teachers' confidence in teaching effectively and influencing student learning (Cansoy & Parlar, 2018; Zheng et al., 2019). School leaders and administrators who offer ongoing professional training, positive reinforcement, and psychological support empower educators to gain confidence in their teaching skills. Consequently, educators develop greater resilience and adaptability, enhancing their teaching effectiveness and boosting student involvement.

Beyond the advantages for individual teachers, instructional leadership influences the wider school culture. An effective instructional leadership strategy cultivates a collaborative and creative school atmosphere where ongoing progress is emphasized. Educators are urged to try innovative teaching methods, assess their instructional approaches, and participate in continuous professional growth. This perpetual learning environment ultimately results in better student achievements and greater success for the institution. Effective instructional leadership is crucial for synchronizing school policies with current educational requirements. In today's age of digital change, instructional leaders need to guarantee that teachers possess the essential skills and tools to incorporate technology successfully into their instructional methods. Offering training programs, technological resources, and creative teaching strategies aids educators in remaining current and improves the educational experience for students. Furthermore, instructional leadership encompasses more than just administrative management; it plays a crucial role in actively influencing the teaching environment and the development of teachers. Instructional leaders cultivate a vibrant educational atmosphere that benefits educators and students by focusing on collaboration among teachers, job satisfaction, dedication, and self-efficacy. Future research should explore how instructional leadership can adjust to new academic challenges, including remote learning and digital teaching methods, to continue enhancing teaching effectiveness and promoting student success. Instructional leadership has gained considerable attention because of its strong emphasis on promoting high-quality teaching and learning (Boyce & Bowers, 2018). A growing number of researchers are acknowledging the essential role that instructional leadership plays in increasing school effectiveness and enhancing student learning outcomes (Karadag, 2020; Shatzer et al., 2014). Over the years, the understanding of instructional leadership has changed. This concept originated in mid-20th-century America, when the term "instructional leaders" replaced "administrators."

In the beginning, instructional leadership was understood in a general sense, focusing on the presence of school leaders in classrooms and their engagement with curriculum and teaching issues (Hallinger & Heck, 1996). Initial studies mainly explored the personal characteristics necessary for effective instructional leadership. As time progressed, the understanding evolved towards a more comprehensive "leadership for learning" model (Hallinger, 2012), which emphasizes the responsibility of school leaders in organizing and overseeing instructional enhancements instead of being directly engaged in everyday teaching activities (Blase & Blase, 2003; Louis et al., 2010; Hallinger et al., 2020).

Blase and Blase (2003) offered a detailed definition of instructional leadership, characterizing it as the management of curriculum, oversight and assessment of teaching, setting and communicating school objectives, being present within the school environment, safeguarding instructional time, providing motivation for learning, and encouraging professional growth. Similarly, Hallinger et al. (2020) defined instructional leadership as school

leadership that impacts teaching and learning to improve student outcomes. Instructional leaders carry out various leadership activities to enhance capabilities and promote learning-centered initiatives throughout the institution. Their duties cover critical aspects such as curriculum development, oversight of instruction, and leadership in assessments, all of which play a role in cultivating a successful and high-quality educational atmosphere. Kasalak and colleagues (2022) performed a meta-analysis investigating the relationship between various leadership styles in higher education institutions and the job satisfaction of academic personnel. The results demonstrated that leadership approaches emphasizing support, clear communication, and efficient operations enhance job satisfaction, which is vital for retention. This suggests that instructional leadership techniques promoting these aspects can improve instructors' retention rates.

Jerrim and Sims (2021) examined how school leadership impacts job satisfaction and staff retention in England's educational framework. Their longitudinal research revealed that positive views of school leadership corresponded with higher job satisfaction and enhanced staff retention rates. Remarkably, with each standard deviation rise in favorable staff views of school leadership, the probability of departing from the school by the next academic year fell from 4.1% to 2.3%. Othman and Busari (2024) conducted a systematic literature review analyzing the effects of instructional leadership on organizational commitment. Their study emphasizes that effective instructional leadership fosters teachers' commitment to their schools, which is crucial for retention. The research highlights the role of school leaders in developing a supportive atmosphere that encourages teacher development and job fulfillment.

Zhan and colleagues (2023) carried out research in less developed regions of Central and Western China to explore the relationship between principals' instructional leadership and the retention of teachers. The results indicated that effective instructional leadership is essential for enhancing teacher retention by reducing stress associated with their roles and bolstering emotional commitment. This chain-mediation effect underscores the importance of supportive leadership in fostering stability among educators, especially in difficult educational environments. Additionally, educators who engaged in ongoing mentorship and professional growth opportunities were notably more inclined to remain in their roles than those who did not have that level of assistance. Instructional leaders who focus on professional development foster a workplace atmosphere where teachers feel empowered, inspired, and involved. Moreover, high workloads and burnout significantly contribute to the turnover of instructors. Research indicates that schools with instructional leaders who effectively oversee teacher workload and allocate adequate resources see reduced teacher turnover rates (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2018). Strong instructional leadership guarantees that teachers are not overwhelmed with too many administrative duties and responsibilities unrelated to teaching, enabling them to focus on instruction and engaging with students (Ladd, 2011). Ensuring a manageable workload and sufficient planning time are essential for boosting instructor retention. Furthermore, research conducted by Othman and Busari (2024) indicates that teachers are more likely to stay in their positions when instructional leaders create a sense of belonging and purpose. Effective leadership promotes a setting where educators feel recognized, valued, and connected to the institution's mission and goals, ultimately increasing retention rates.

Factors Affecting Instructor Retention. The retention of faculty in higher education is crucial not only for preserving academic standards but also for providing a stable and enriching educational experience for students. When professors depart, it disrupts the continuity of courses, obstructs student advancement, and may adversely affect the institution's reputation (Baker, 2014). Additionally, high turnover rates can put pressure on the remaining faculty, resulting in burnout and lowered morale, which worsens retention issues. A consistent teaching staff promotes a collaborative and involved academic community, creating a setting where teachers and students can flourish. Thus, institutions should focus on comprehending the elements that affect faculty retention to cultivate a supportive and efficient educational environment.

Grasping how different educational leadership styles affect faculty retention is crucial for developing effective methods to improve job satisfaction and commitment among educators. Studies show that leadership styles, like transformational leadership, correlate positively with increased job satisfaction and retention rates (Chen et al., 2021; Miller, 2016). Transformational leaders encourage and energize faculty by creating a shared sense of purpose and teamwork, whereas servant leaders focus on their staff's welfare and career development. Conversely, more transactional leadership approaches can lead to feelings of detachment and underappreciation among faculty, which may eventually cause increased turnover (Northouse, 2018). By identifying and adjusting leadership approaches to align with faculty needs, higher education institutions can greatly enhance retention rates and foster a more supportive and efficient academic atmosphere. Abbas and Ali (2021) noted that

transformational leadership primarily emphasizes interpersonal relationships, while transactional leadership is centered around task completion. Similarly, Boehnke et al. (2003) argued that transformational leadership aligns more closely with the personal needs of followers, whereas transactional leadership concentrates heavily on organizational procedures. The skills and behaviors that leaders require to foster greater innovation and manage change are a crucial topic within many organizations (Bass et al., 2003). Specific leadership styles and actions are essential for organizations to transform, and this research could assist in pinpointing the advantages of transformational leadership that contribute to successful change management within organizations.

Successful strategies for retaining employees are crucial for maintaining organizational stability and generating revenue. Employees are critical assets of any organization (Kossivi & Kalgora, 2016). Leaders within organizations encounter the challenge of replacing 70 million skilled and experienced workers (Oladapo, 2014). Furthermore, studies indicate that keeping employees engaged is difficult because various individuals are driven by distinct retention approaches, including opportunities for training and development, performance reviews, and compensation, all of which are vital components of their work (Mohamed et al., 2014). A method for keeping employees is implementing reward programs that acknowledge employees for their excellent performance (Ferreira & Almeida, 2015). When leaders appreciate their employees' contributions, they often increase happiness and job satisfaction. To stay competitive and reduce employee turnover, managers must enhance or build upon their retention strategies to attract, recruit, nurture, and keep valuable staff. Researchers have characterized retention as the process in which employees are motivated to stay with their employer for an adequate duration (Gupta & Singh, 2014; Kossivi & Kalgora, 2016). Sandhya and Kumar (2015) state that employee retention involves a coordinated effort by employers to create a workplace atmosphere that promotes the desire for existing employees to stay with the company. In a competitive business environment, leaders face challenges and concerns related to this task (Terera & Nigirande, 2014). As a result, it has become increasingly vital for organizations to handle and endure turnover effectively. Similarly, Martin (2015) observed that maintaining employee retention has become one of the most significant challenges for management regarding the future workforce. Similarly, Sypniewska (2014) emphasized that companies encounter difficulties in reducing turnover linked to insufficient job satisfaction, inadequate skills, training, knowledge, and leadership. Employee retention strategies are essential components of an organization's operational best practices. Replacing skilled and knowledgeable employees includes recruitment expenses to fill open positions and training costs. Implementing effective retention strategies can assist in retaining key employees.

In 2015, Cloutier et al. highlighted that workflow interruptions can hinder a business's success. The challenge of retaining employees complicates preserving a positive workplace culture and morale. As technology progresses, the workforce must enhance their skills, making retaining valuable employees vital for an organization's stability, growth, and income (Aruna & Anitha, 2015; Darkwa et al., 2015). Consequently, managers must apply retention strategies that enhance the business's capacity to develop with greater proficiency, increased innovation, and enduring strategic business goals (Mahesh, 2017). Furthermore, employees who grasp the retention strategies contribute more effectively to the organization's well-being (Ashmore & Gilson, 2015). Create initiatives that improve the workflow within the organization. As a result, keeping employees and implementing strategies that support the organization are vital components of the organization's vision, mission, values, and policies. Nonetheless, creating training programs for employees, clarifying their expectations, and offering a safe space for them to voice concerns without the worry of backlash are enduring strategies for retention that enable a business to thrive (Mahesh, 2017). Mentoring initiatives play an essential role in professional growth and considerably affect faculty retention. A study by Johnson (2007) shows that faculty who engage in mentoring relationships experience enhanced job satisfaction and a more profound sense of belonging to their institutions. Mentoring offers educators guidance, support, and a platform to address challenges within a secure setting. This connection encourages professional development and is especially advantageous for new faculty members, assisting them in managing the intricacies of academic life. Consequently, institutions that emphasize mentorship play a key role in creating a nurturing environment that boosts retention.

Chances for leadership growth are essential for promoting faculty retention. According to Miller (2016), when faculty are motivated to assume leadership positions within their departments or institutions, they experience an increased sense of ownership and commitment to their work. Leadership development programs can enable educators to participate in decision-making, increasing their involvement and dedication. By cultivating leadership abilities, faculty members are prepared to progress in their careers while also serving as champions for their departments, promoting a more constructive institutional environment that aids retention. Employee satisfaction and effective leadership are critical factors in determining whether an individual stays with their employer and

aids in the organization's success or chooses to leave, negatively impacting the organization (Alex & George, 2014). Similarly, Ahmad and Rainyee (2014) highlighted that employees' commitment to their organization and overall job satisfaction significantly influence turnover rates and absenteeism. Additionally, Ahmad et al. (2014) discovered that employees who receive constructive feedback, enjoy job security, and have flexible work schedules that accommodate their lifestyles are more likely to remain with the organization.

Various researchers have recognized job satisfaction as a key factor in attracting and keeping skilled employees (Kumar et al., 2014). Several factors impact job satisfaction, including the relationships between supervisors and employees, salary, benefits, incentives, leadership styles, communication, coworkers, acknowledgment, and opportunities for career growth (Mohammad et al., 2011). According to the research conducted by Terera and Ngirande (2014), rewards and job satisfaction significantly influence employee retention. Additionally, opportunities for training and development, promotion, and performance management play a crucial role in enhancing employee job satisfaction. Compensation also plays a significant part in an employee's decision to remain with or leave a company. Employees are interested in understanding the company's benefits that benefit them and their families. An alternative strategy for retention is fostering employee engagement, which studies have shown can help decrease turnover rates. Departments with high employee engagement generally experience lower turnover (Mumtaz, 2016). As a result, an organization must establish a retention strategy emphasizing job satisfaction and compensation as key elements.

Work Environment and Culture. Baker (2014) states that organizations that offer sufficient resources, including access to technology and opportunities for professional development, foster an environment that empowers instructors to thrive, resulting in increased retention rates. Institutional culture encompasses an academic environment's collective values, beliefs, and practices. A robust, positive culture that fosters collaboration, inclusivity, and mutual respect can substantially affect faculty retention. Research conducted by Gunter (2016) indicates that institutions characterized by shared governance, such as educators, tend to stay at institutions where they believe their opinions are acknowledged. Their efforts are appreciated, leading to decreased turnover rates (Harris, 2004). A supportive environment cultivates a feeling of inclusion, essential for retaining faculty. The relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction is essential in retaining instructors. Educators frequently encounter difficulties in managing their professional duties alongside personal obligations.

Recognition and Support. Acknowledging the contributions of faculty members is crucial for improving job satisfaction and retention. A study conducted by Chen et al. (2021) shows that when organizations make a concerted effort to recognize their faculty's accomplishments and hard work, it cultivates a feeling of belonging and commitment. Instructors who receive recognition through awards, positive feedback, or formal acknowledgment during meetings often feel esteemed and valued. As noted by Miller (2016), such recognition enhances morale and encourages faculty to become more involved in their teaching and research duties, ultimately resulting in higher retention rates. The support systems offered by institutions play a crucial role in retaining faculty by meeting their professional and personal requirements. Institutions that provide firm support, including mentoring initiatives, opportunities for professional growth, and mental health services, enable faculty to manage challenges more effectively. The study conducted by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) highlights that mentoring connections can improve job satisfaction and diminish feelings of isolation among faculty, leading to better retention rates. Additionally, an administration that provides support and addresses faculty issues creates a setting where instructors feel appreciated and secure, supporting their ongoing dedication to the institution.

Transformational leadership as a retention strategy. The approach of transformational leadership in keeping employees extends past the simple transactions between managers and their teams. While these transactions are essential for employee job satisfaction, transformational leaders concentrate on supporting and enhancing the growth of their subordinates (Patiar, & Wang, 2016). Embracing a suitable leadership approach enables leaders to tackle essential issues and surmount difficulties (Sethuraman & Suresh, 2014). The type of leadership employed influences employee growth and their dedication to the organization (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Swamy, 2015). Transformational leadership fosters an environment that promotes a positive workplace for employees. Leaders who employ this leadership style motivate their team members to surpass their expectations, directly influencing the outcomes the leader attains. Transformational leaders foster a sense of confidence that enhances employee productivity and job satisfaction while reducing turnover rates (Yao et al., 2014). Transformational leaders and their followers inspire one another to reach higher levels of inspiration and ethical standards (Burns, 1978). Additionally, transformational leadership is more effective than transactional or laissez-faire leadership regarding

job satisfaction and employee retention (Kumar et al., 2014). How a leader behaves and guides their team can significantly influence whether a follower chooses to support them or not.

The attention given by transformational leaders establishes a strong base for the manager and their team, helping to minimize employee turnover (Root, 2016). Additionally, transformational leaders strive to engage with and illuminate the potential in every employee (Perko, Kinnunen, & Feldt, 2014). These managers dedicate time to support their employees by creating methods that simplify their tasks and assist them in advancing their careers (Kumar et al., 2014). Transformational leaders prioritize the well-being of their employees, which typically alleviates stress and work-related pressures while boosting employees' self-esteem. This, in turn, leads to higher levels of job satisfaction (Salem, 2015). Transformational leaders leveraged their influence to inspire employees to reach their objectives and the organization's goals by serving as role models.

In addition, leaders within an organization have a crucial influence on the business results, particularly concerning employee attitudes, commitment, and the company's financial status (Robertson & Barling, 2013). Love, Trammell, and Cartner (2010) illustrated how effective transformational leadership can be as a strategy for retention, particularly aimed at enhancing minority representation and keeping students in predominantly white institutions of higher education. By emphasizing the learning styles of diverse groups, transformational leaders enhanced the capability to adapt teaching methods and accommodate the learning needs of different groups. A collective vision and dedication to institutional reform fostered a creative learning atmosphere that involved a united community and resulted in enhanced retention and academic achievement for minority groups. Additionally, as highlighted by Love et al., establishing diversity and equal educational opportunities within institutions necessitates enacting change through transformational leadership, which fosters a learning atmosphere that involves a collective community. As a result, transformational leadership can enhance employee morale and increase job satisfaction (Asrar-ul-Hag & Kuchinke, 2016). Certain studies have indicated that the traits and behaviors associated with transformational leadership positively influence organizations in terms of teamwork success, effectiveness, employee satisfaction, commitment, and the promotion of work-related values among followers, as well as fostering followers' self-efficacy (Mah'd et al., 2014). Transformational leaders' actions significantly influence the organization's daily operations, fostering employee commitment, which subsequently promotes retention.

Transactional leadership as a retention strategy. Research suggests that transactional leadership may lead to favorable retention results, especially in larger educational organizations with common hierarchical frameworks. For instance, a study conducted by Houghton and Yoho (2005) indicates that transactional leadership may improve job satisfaction by offering explicit rewards and acknowledgment for achievements, potentially resulting in higher retention rates among faculty. Faculty members who feel their efforts are acknowledged and rewarded tend to show greater commitment to their institutions. Additionally, research by Chen et al. (2021) indicates that transactional leadership, when paired with strong communication and support mechanisms, leads to increased job satisfaction and higher retention rates among faculty. The success of transactional leadership as a strategy for retention frequently depends on the specific context in which it is utilized. Transactional leadership tends to be especially effective in settings that prioritize accountability and result-driven approaches. According to research by Al-Ali and Al-Qudah (2020), organizations that emphasize performance metrics can utilize transactional leadership to foster a motivating atmosphere that inspires faculty to achieve set objectives, improving retention. Additionally, transactional leadership can act as a basis for creating defined avenues for professional advancement, motivating faculty members to remain in their positions (Baker, 2014).

Although transactional leadership has positively impacted employee retention, its effectiveness can be improved when integrated with transformational methods. Studies indicate that leaders utilizing a blended strategy—mixing defined rewards with inspirational encouragement—can foster a more stimulating workplace atmosphere (Miller, 2016). This integration enables acknowledgment of performance and promotes intrinsic motivation, resulting in greater job satisfaction and faculty dedication. By utilizing both leadership approaches, institutions can create a well-rounded retention strategy that caters to various faculty requirements.

Instructional Leadership style as a retention strategy. Instructional leadership is vital in improving teacher involvement and professional growth, both essential for retaining staff. Magboo et al. (2023) examined how school leaders' instructional leadership behaviors relate to teachers' work engagement in public elementary schools. The research revealed a significant positive relationship, suggesting that strong instructional leadership enhances teachers' vigor, dedication, and absorption. Increased involvement leads to greater job satisfaction and

lowers the likelihood of employees wanting to leave. Additionally, He et al. (2024) explored how school principals' instructional leadership can predict teachers' professional growth in Nigeria. The results showed that school leaders who actively promote and offer chances for professional advancement significantly improve teachers' growth, resulting in higher job satisfaction and better retention rates. These research findings highlight the significance of instructional leadership in fostering supportive environments that encourage teacher development and retention in their careers.

Theoretical Framework

This research is based on the Transformational Leadership Theory developed by Bernard Bass in 1985. This theory asserts that leaders collaborate with their teams to recognize necessary changes, formulate a vision to steer the change, and implement it alongside dedicated members. Studies indicate that when educational leaders display transformational leadership qualities, teachers experience higher satisfaction, engagement, and commitment to their institutions. These favorable working conditions enhance teacher retention by lowering turnover rates, boosting job satisfaction, and encouraging professional development. Schools led by transformational leaders often foster a more supportive school environment, which is a critical element in retaining teachers. According to this theoretical framework concerning educational leadership practices, the transformational leadership theory outlines three approaches for leaders to enhance motivation among teachers. First, it involves elevating followers' awareness of the significance and value of the intended outcomes and the methods to achieve them. Second, it encourages followers to rise above their self-interest for the benefit of the team, organization, or greater community. Finally, it aims to elevate followers' needs to higher-level needs, such as self-actualization, or by broadening their range of needs.

Much research has been conducted to clarify the mechanics of transformational leadership. Typically, four key components arise: creativity, objectives, vision, and dedication. 1Creativity, transformational leaders tend to be more effective as they express their creativity, which inspires their followers to be more inventive. These leaders are proactive instead of reactive; imaginative rather than submissive; and bold instead of conventional. Goals: Individuals who follow transformational leaders are more inclined to strive for challenging objectives, comprehend and align with the organization's official goals, and have confidence that the goals they are working toward will contribute to their fulfillment. Transformational leaders develop a strategic vision that motivates and brings their followers together. They communicate the vision with emotional appeal that captivates followers and other stakeholders. Commitment: Transformational leaders cultivate dedication to the vision by demonstrating passion for every endeavor they undertake, being relentless in executing all initiatives, and engaging their followers in developing the vision. Transformational leadership is expected to positively correlate with leader effectiveness assessments, organizational or group performance, and follower job satisfaction and motivation. The concepts outlined above provided the foundation that guides the implementation of this research.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Locale

The study was conducted in Davao de Oro, a province in the Davao Region and the location of Davao de Oro State College (DDOSC), which operates multiple campuses across the province. The New Bataan Campus, located in the 1st class municipality of New Bataan, offers three academic programs: Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED), Bachelor of Secondary Education with majors in Mathematics, English, and Social Studies (BSED), and a non-board program, Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship. The Maragusan Campus, situated in the 1st class municipality of Maragusan, provides four academic programs, including board-licensed degrees in BEED and BSED with majors in Mathematics, English, and Social Studies, along with Bachelor of Science in Agriculture and Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship. The Montevista Campus, located in the Municipality of Montevista, offers three academic programs including BEED, BSED with majors in Mathematics, English, Social Studies, and Filipino, and a non-board program in Entrepreneurship. Lastly, the Compostela Campus, also known as the Main Campus and located in the Municipality of Compostela, offers five academic programs: BEED, BSED with majors in Mathematics, English, and Biological Science, along with Bachelor of Science in Agriculture and Bachelor of Science in Entrepreneurship. All campuses contribute to the academic landscape of Davao de Oro by offering a mix of board and non-board degree programs.

Design

The study utilized a quantitative descriptive ex-post facto research design. The choice of a quantitative approach is based on the existing trends in the research field at the study site (Creswell, 2012). This approach was suitable when researchers aimed to explain the reasons behind occurrences. Describe trends involved in examining overall

patterns of responses among individuals and noting variations in these patterns. Given these considerations, the quantitative approach was deemed most appropriate for this study. Moreover, the correlation approach was utilized to assess the relationship between the effects of various educational leadership styles and teacher retention. This is by Creswell (2012), who states that correlational research designs employ statistical correlation tests to describe and evaluate the strength of association between two or more variables or sets of scores.

Respondents

The respondents were selected through universal sampling. The researcher considered purposive sampling since all faculty members from the main campus and other campuses within Davao de Oro will be the respondents. There are 28 respondents who met the qualification based on the nature of this study.

Instrument

Quantitative data were gathered through the survey questionnaire, which the researcher modified. Three questionnaires were used to collect the data. One questionnaire from Sunaengsih et al. (2021) is used to determine the instructors in rating the institution's current situation of transformational leadership style. The second questionnaire from Akhigbe (2014) is used to determine the instructors in rating the current situation of transactional leadership style of the institution. The third questionnaire from Kilag & Sasan (2023) determines the instructors' current instructional leadership style in the institution. At the same time, the data on the retention rate of teachers will be taken from the records kept by the office of the school president or the office of human resource management. The four-point Likert scale below will aid the statistical interpretation of the research questionnaire.

Weight	Categories
4	Highly Practiced (Very Frequently)
3	Rarely Practice, (Frequently)
2	Moderately Practice (Occasionally)
1	Never (At no time)

Validation

The questionnaires used in this study were separated into two. One questionnaire from Sunaengsih et.al. (2021) is used to determine the instructors in rating of the institution's current situation of transformational leadership style. The second questionnaire from Akhigbe (2014) was used to determine the instructors in ratings the current situation of transactional leadership style of the institution. However, the researcher modified the questionnaires to fit into what was asked for the study. The questionnaire was validated by the experts identified by the Dean of the Graduate School.

Procedure

First, the researcher secured a certificate of approval from the ethics committee of the Assumption College of Nabunturan before the research was given the signal to conduct such study. The researcher also wrote a letter to the college president requesting approval for the study. When permission was granted, the researcher presented the letter of acceptance to the program heads and program coordinators of all the academic departments on all campuses to inform them of the study. The researcher will follow the REC (Research Ethics Committee) protocol before gathering data. The questionnaire administration was set through an online survey, given that the researcher and the respondents followed the standard protocol set by the data privacy unit.

The nature and scope of the study were embedded in the online survey questionnaire. The researcher conducted the data collection by administering the online survey to all college-graduate instructors. The researcher then checked and saved the files in the Google Drive for backup. For the analysis and the interpretation of the data, this study used descriptive statistics. The administration of the questionnaire to the instructor-respondents of the Davao de Oro State College was based on the convenient time and place since it was done through an online survey.

Treatment of Data

This study used descriptive statistics to analyze and interpret the collected data. Mean and standard deviation will be used to describe the relationship between educational leadership style and the level of instructors' retention rate, and the extent to which the educational leadership styles of academic leaders affect the retention rate of instructors in the institution will be examined.

Ethical Considerations

According to Bhashin (2020), ethical consideration presents the beliefs and concepts that should be maintained throughout the study. With this, the researcher ensured that the ethical standards were strictly followed throughout the study, addressing the areas that follow: This research was done to answer the existing issues in attaining the organizational objectives of one of the Higher Education Institutions of Davao de Oro. This study aimed to determine which leadership styles influence the retention rate in the institution. The results were shared with the academic community of Davao de Oro State College. They were published in the online journal so that other related research studies can use it as a reference. The researcher distributed Informed Consent Forms (ICF) to the identified respondents. The researcher disclosed essential information, such as the researcher's name and affiliation. It was also emphasized that the respondents' participation was purely voluntary, and they were free to withdraw anytime they felt discomfort. The purpose of the study was also explained, along with the procedures carried out for the study. The researcher explained the entire data gathering process and emphasized that the respondents had the freedom to opt out during the process if they experienced any discomfort, which would not affect them in any way. The researcher explained the benefits of the respondent's participation in the study. The data gathering process was done at the most convenient time and place for the respondents, and the researcher reimbursed them for any expenses they incurred for the study. The researcher made sure that the respondent's personal information, identity, and data gathered were kept confidential and secured to ensure that the Data Privacy Act of 2012 was being followed. The data collected was kept on Google Drive, which only the researcher can access. The data were destroyed after the study was conducted. The research respondents were chosen based on the inclusion criteria: they must be faculty members of at least five years in service and come from different genders and economic statuses. In any case, the research respondents might incur their expenses during the conduct of the study, and the researcher reimbursed them. They were also given a token of appreciation for the inconvenience the study might have caused. To address this aspect, the researcher disclosed the study's affiliations and objective. The research respondents were given a copy of their responses to verify the reliability and validity of the data gathered. The researcher had enough experience in conducting a study during college and graduate school studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of the Educational Leadership Style of Academic Leaders

This section presents the results addressing the first statement of the problem, which examines the level of educational leadership style of academic leaders in terms of transformational, transactional, and instructional leadership, as well as the retention rate of instructors in the institution.

Educational Leadership Style in terms of Transformational. Table 1 presents the level of educational leadership style of academic leaders in terms of transformational. Table 2 shows the educational leadership style of academic leaders in terms of transformational leadership based on the twenty-five items rated by the instructors. The mean scores range from 3.30 to 3.63, the highest mean was recorded in item 3 “reminds every instructor to respect each other including non-teaching staffs.” with a mean score of 3.63 and a descriptive rating of “Highly Practice”. Items 2, 1, 8, and 17 yielded mean scores of 3.59, 3.56, 3.56 and 3.52, respectively, each with a descriptive rating the same of the highest mean as “Highly Practice”, these mean scores were the first five highest among the items, while the lowest mean score recorded in the item 11 “checks the results of the evaluation to make up for any shortcomings” and item 12 “guides and trains instructors personally if they have problems” with both has a mean score of 3.30 and a descriptive rating of “Rarely Practice”. The overall mean for the transformational leadership style is 3.44 described as “Rarely Practice”.

Table 1. Level of Transformational Leadership Style of Academic Leaders

Indicator	Mean Rating	Descriptive Rating
1. provides insight and awareness of the vision, mission, and goals.	3.56	Highly Practice
2. carries out tasks in accordance with the vision, mission, and goals	3.59	Highly Practice
3. reminds every instructor to respect each other including non-teaching staffs.	3.63	Highly Practice
4. grows an attitude of respect by setting the leaders as example of good behavior in the college environment.	3.48	Rarely Practice
5. increases intelligence by equitable provision of professional development.	3.37	Rarely Practice

6. provides freedom of opinion regarding policies in higher education.	3.37	Rarely Practice
7. involves instructors in assessing the activities in the college.	3.48	Rarely Practice
8. the head/dean per program has a way of solving complex problems.	3.56	Highly Practice
9. gives praise and appreciation to the work results or achievements of the instructors	3.48	Rarely Practice
10. asks for the opinion regarding the leadership pathway.	3.37	Rarely Practice
11. checks the results of the evaluation to make up for any shortcomings.	3.30	Rarely Practice
12. guides and trains instructors personally if they have problems.	3.30	Rarely Practice
13. knows the needs of instructors for the flow of the teaching and learning activities in the classroom.	3.48	Rarely Practice
14.gives attention by listening to the complaints of instructors for mutual comfort.	3.37	Rarely Practice
15. influences instructors to be optimistic in facing the future.	3.37	Rarely Practice
16. gives recognition for the works of instructors in the form of personal praise.	3.48	Rarely Practice
17. gives enthusiasm to instructors to carry out their tasks properly.	3.52	Highly Practice
18. supports instructors to get good results in teaching in the classroom.	3.37	Rarely Practice
19. tells the success stories of colleagues to motivate instructors to be successful in their respective field of specialization.	3.48	Rarely Practice
20. encourages instructors to work hard professionally.	3.41	Rarely Practice
21. gives enthusiasm to instructors for finding other methods of solving-problems regarding teaching and learning activities in the classroom.	3.48	Rarely Practice
22. encourages instructors to practice new approaches in implementing teaching and learning activities.	3.41	Rarely Practice
23. communicates the goals that must be achieved by instructors clearly.	3.37	Rarely Practice
24. gives appreciation/praise to instructors for completing their work well.	3.44	Rarely Practice
25. provides special time for instructors to discuss how to complete assignments properly	3.37	Rarely Practice
Overall Mean	3.44	Rarely Practice

Educational Leadership Style in terms of Transactional

Table 2. Level of Transformational Leadership Style of Academic Leaders

Indicators	Mean Rating	Descriptive Rating
1. provides me with assistance in exchange for my efforts.	3.40	Rarely Practice
2. discusses in specific terms that is responsible for achieving performance targets.	3.48	Rarely Practice
3. makes clear what one can expect to receive when performance goals are achieved.	3.52	Highly Practice
4. expresses satisfaction when I meet expectations.	3.41	Rarely Practice
5. makes innovative suggestions to improve the college.	3.44	Rarely Practice
6. focuses attention on irregularities, mistakes, and exceptions.	3.30	Rarely Practice
7. concentrates on dealing with mistakes, complains and failures.	3.15	Rarely Practice
8. keeps track of all mistakes.	3.19	Rarely Practice
9. directs the attention to failures to conform to the standards.	3.15	Rarely Practice
10. interferes problems becomes so that it will not get serious or worsen.	3.38	Rarely Practice
11. waits for things to go wrong before taking action.	3.22	Rarely Practice
12. demonstrates that problems must become chronic before to take action.	3.04	Rarely Practice

Overall Mean	3.31	Rarely Practice
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Table 3 shows that level of educational leadership style of academic leaders in terms of transactional based on the 12 items rated by the instructors. The mean scores range from 3.04 to 3.52, the highest mean was recorded in item 3 “makes clear what one can expect to receive when performance goals are achieved”, with a mean score of 3.52 and a descriptive rating of “Highly Practice”. Items 2, 5, 4, and 1 yielded mean scores of 3.48, 3.44, 3.41 and 3.40, respectively, each with a descriptive rating of “Rarely Practice”, while the lowest mean score recorded in item 12 “demonstrates that problems must become chronic before to take action” with a mean score of 3.04 and descriptive rating of “Rarely Practice”. The overall mean for the transactional leadership style is 3.31 described as “Rarely Practice”.

Educational Leadership Style in terms of Instructional. Table 3 presents the level of instructional leadership style of academic leaders. Table 4 shows that level of educational leadership style of academic leaders in terms of instructional based on the 12 items rated by the instructors. The mean scores range from 3.37 to 4, the highest mean was recorded in item 1 “supports teachers’ instructional methods and their modifications of instructional approaches and materials”, with a mean score of 4 and a descriptive rating of “Highly Practice”. Item 6 had a mean score 3.52 followed by items 4, 8, 9 and 12 which yielded the same mean score of 3.48 and a descriptive rating of “Rarely Practice”, while the lowest mean was recorded in item 7 “leads in the creation of an innovation vision shared by all members of the organization” with a mean score of 3.37 and a descriptive rating of “Rarely Practice”. The overall mean for the instructional leadership style is 3.49 described as “Rarely Practice”.

Table 3. Level of Instructional Leadership Style of Academic Leaders

Indicator	Mean Rating	Descriptive Rating
1. supports teachers’ instructional methods and their modifications of instructional approaches and materials	4	Highly Practice
2. allocates resources and materials providing that it may help the students to improve their academic performance	3.44	Rarely Practice
3. visits classrooms for instructional purposes	3.38	Highly Practice
4. solicits and provides feedback on instructional methods and techniques of other schools for benchmarking.	3.48	Rarely Practice
5. sees and finds potentials and opportunities even amidst the problems academically.	3.44	Rarely Practice
6. creates an environment where teachers can realize their peak performance and have the freedom of creativity.	3.52	Highly Practice
7. leads in the creation of an innovation vision shared by all members of the organization	3.37	Rarely Practice
8. ensures that the vision becomes reality by stating clear goals, outlining a strategic plan for achieving those goals.	3.48	Rarely Practice
9. generates ideas and explore opportunities that encourage teachers to come up with their own ideas	3.48	Rarely Practice
10. provides continuous guidance on innovation related to education	3.44	Rarely Practice
11. leads to use data and faculty input to determine staff development activities that strengthen teachers’ instructional skills	3.44	Rarely Practice
12. allows instructors to propel innovation and show initiative which is the key to successful workplace revival	3.48	Rarely Practice
Overall Mean	3.49	Rarely Practice

Summary on the extent of Educational Leadership Styles

Table 4. Summary on the extent of Educational Leadership Styles

Indicator	Mean Rating	Description
Transformational Leadership Style	3.44	Rarely Practice
Transactional Leadership Style	3.31	Rarely Practice
Instructional Leadership Style	3.49	Rarely Practice
Overall Mean	3.41	Rarely Practice

The table presents the summary of the educational leadership style of the institution in terms of transformational, transactional, and instructional. The mean score of all leadership styles falls within the “Rarely Practice” descriptive rating and a mean score of 3.41, indicating that all the academic leaders of the institution vastly practice all the educational leadership styles across all branches. Owing to the result, the instructional leadership style recorded the highest mean of 3.49, followed by transformational leadership style with 3.44 and the lowest mean was observed in transactional leadership style at 3.31.

Extent of the Retention Rate of Instructors in the Institution

This section presents the results of addressing the second statement of the problem, which examines the extent of instructor’s retention rate in the institution. Shown in table 5 are the mean score and descriptive rating based on the 12 items rated by the instructors.

Table 5. Extent of the Retention Rate of Instructors in the Institution

Indicator	Mean Rating	Description
1. I am committed to teaching as a career.	3.44	Rarely Practice
2. If I could go back to my college days, I would choose teaching as a career again.	3.33	Rarely Practice
3. I would encourage college bound students to enter teaching as a career.	3.44	Rarely Practice
4. family factors (e.g. marriage, birth, relocation) would account for me leaving teaching or interrupting my career in teaching.	3.15	Rarely Practice
5. economic factors would account for me leaving teaching or interrupting my career in teaching.	3.22	Rarely Practice
6. I am satisfied with my teaching salary.	3.52	Highly Practice
7. I am satisfied with my opportunities to collaborate among the staff.	3.44	Rarely Practice
8. I am satisfied with the degree of administrative support and teacher’s recognition in the college.	3.41	Rarely Practice
9. directs the attention to failures to conform to the standards.	3.33	Rarely Practice
10. I am amenable to all policies and regulations administratively and academically in the college.	3.48	Rarely Practice
11. reflecting on my college career, I would again choose teaching as a career choice.	3.30	Rarely Practice
12. I intend to stay in the college more than 10 years.	3.30	Rarely Practice
Overall Mean	3.36	Rarely Practice

Table 5 shows the extent of the retention rate of instructors in the institution. The mean scores range from 3.15 to 3.52, the highest mean was recorded in item 6 “I am satisfied with my teaching salary”, with a mean score of 3.52 and a descriptive rating of “Highly Practice”. Item 10 had a mean score 3.48 with a descriptive rating of “Rarely Practice”, followed by items 1, 3, 7 all three has the same mean score of 3.44 with descriptive rating of “Rarely Practice” also, while the lowest mean was recorded in item 4 “family factors (e.g. marriage, birth, relocation) would account for me leaving teaching or interrupting my career in teaching” with a mean score of 3.15 and a descriptive rating of “Rarely Practice”. The overall mean for the instructors’ retention rate is 3.36 described as “Rarely Practice”.

Table 6 Relationship Between Educational Leadership Style and Instructors’ Retention Rate in the Institution

Pearson Correlations		Transformational	Transactional	Instructional
Retention	Pearson's r	0.550	0.508	0.687
	p-value	0.003	0.007	< .001
Remarks	Significant	Significant	Significant	

Table 6 reflects that the transformational leadership style which has the Pearson's r of 0.550 with p-value of 0.003 suggesting a strong positive relationship between transformational leadership style and instructors’ retention rate, which is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Given the outcome, the null hypothesis stating “there is no significant relationship between the transformational leadership style and the retention rate of teachers” is rejected. In addition, the transactional leadership style with the Pearson’s r of 0.508 with p-value of 0.003 indicates

a significant relationship between transactional leadership style and instructors' retention rate. With this effect, the null hypothesis stating "there is no significant relationship between the transactional leadership style and the retention rate of teachers" is also rejected. Moreover, the instructional leadership style with the Pearson's r of 0.687 with p -value of $<.001$ likewise indicates a significant relationship between instructional leadership and the retention rate of instructors, for which it is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Considering the outcome, the null hypothesis stating "there is no significant relationship between the instructional leadership style and the retention rate of teachers" is similarly rejected.

The level of educational leadership style of academic leaders in Davao de Oro State College in terms of Transformational. The results concerning transformational leadership revealed that while the overall practice is rated as "Rarely Practice", there are specific indicators where academic leaders are perceived to "Highly Practice" transformational behaviors. Notably, "reminds every instructor to respect each other, including non-teaching staffs" scored the highest mean, followed by "carries out tasks in accordance with the vision, mission, and goals" and "provides insight and awareness of the vision, mission, and goals". Conversely, items such as "checks the results of the evaluation to make up for any shortcomings" and "guides and trains instructors personally if they have problems" both received the lowest mean, indicating areas where transformational leadership is minimally practiced.

The disparity between highly practiced ethical and vision-oriented behaviors and minimally practiced developmental aspects of transformational leadership indicates a nuanced application of this style within the institution. While leaders excel at fostering respect and aligning tasks with institutional goals, their infrequent engagement in personal guidance, training, and evaluation follow-up suggests a gap in individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation, key tenets of transformational leadership. This imbalance could limit instructors' opportunities for professional growth and problem-solving, potentially affecting their long-term satisfaction and commitment, thereby impeding the institution's overall instructor retention efforts. This finding generally coincides with transformational leadership, which focuses on motivating followers and cultivating a collective vision. According to Bass and Riggio (2006) and Choi et al. (2016), transformational leaders encourage employees to exceed expected performance levels and achieve high satisfaction and commitment. Nevertheless, the lower ratings in individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation indicate a departure from the full application of this leadership approach as outlined by scholars like Northouse (2013), who asserts that transformational leaders guide, mentor, and instruct their followers, and motivate them to think beyond their usual boundaries.

Recent studies underscore the importance of a holistic approach to transformational leadership for positive organizational outcomes. For example, a 2021 study by Khan et al. on higher education faculty revealed that leaders exhibiting strong individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation significantly impacted faculty performance and retention. Similarly, research by Susanto et al. (2020) demonstrated that while vision and inspirational motivation are crucial, the consistent provision of intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration by transformational leaders is vital for fostering a thriving academic environment and enhancing employee loyalty. These contemporary findings suggest that addressing the less-practiced aspects of transformational leadership could significantly improve instructor retention at the college.

The level of educational leadership style of academic leaders in Davao de Oro State College in terms of Transactional. The assessment of transactional leadership style reveals an overall "Rarely Practice". The highest mean score was recorded in item 3, "makes clear what one can expect to receive when performance goals are achieved,". Conversely, the lowest mean score was observed in item 12, "demonstrates that problems must become chronic before to take action," Other items, such as "provides me with assistance in exchange for my efforts" and "expresses satisfaction when I meet expectations" were also rated as "Rarely Practice".

This pattern of results indicates that while academic leaders are somewhat effective in clarifying performance expectations and rewards, they infrequently engage in active or even passive management-by-exception. The low scores in addressing problems proactively or demonstrating responsiveness only when issues become chronic suggest a reactive approach rather than a proactive or corrective one. This could lead to a lack of clear consequences for underperformance or insufficient recognition for meeting expectations, potentially demotivating instructors and failing to address underlying issues promptly, thereby negatively impacting retention.

The "Highly Practice" in making expectations clear aligns with the core of transactional leadership, which focuses on exchanges and goal achievement. However, the overall "Rarely Practice" rating, particularly in corrective actions, suggests that the transactional leadership observed is not fully aligned with the balanced approach described in the literature. Kuhnert and Lewis (1987) indicate that transactional leadership involves an exchange where both leaders and followers influence each other and gain something of value, which implies a more consistent application of contingent reward and management-by-exception, not just the former. Recent research on transactional leadership in academic settings provides further context. A study by Ghaffari et al. (2020) on university faculty found that while contingent reward (clarifying expectations and rewards) positively influenced job satisfaction, passive management-by-exception (waiting for problems to become chronic) significantly correlated with lower faculty morale and higher turnover intentions. Similarly, research by Su et al. (2021) in Chinese universities highlighted that effective transactional leadership requires a balance of contingent reward and active management-by-exception to ensure accountability and address issues before they escalate, reinforcing that a lack of proactive problem-solving can undermine instructor retention.

The level of educational leadership style of academic leaders in Davao de Oro State College in terms of Instructional. The findings on instructional leadership indicate an overall "Rarely Practice" descriptive rating. The item "supports teachers' instructional methods and their modifications of instructional approaches and materials" received the highest mean score. Other indicators, such as "creates an environment where teachers can realize their peak performance and have the freedom of creativity" and "visits classrooms for instructional purposes" (3.38), also received "Highly Practice" ratings. Conversely, "leads in the creation of an innovation vision shared by all members of the organization," was rated "Rarely Practice".

Despite some aspects of instructional support being highly practiced, the overall "Rarely Practice" rating suggests that academic leaders are not consistently fulfilling the full scope of instructional leadership. While they may actively support teaching methods and foster creative environments, there appears to be a gap in leading innovative visions. This inconsistency implies that while individual instructional needs might be addressed, a broader, collective commitment to instructional innovation may be lacking. This could limit the institution's ability to adapt to new educational challenges and retain instructors who seek dynamic and forward-thinking professional development opportunities.

The support for instructional methods and creative environments aligns with the literature emphasizing instructional leadership's role in professional development and engagement. Magboo et al. (2023) found a significant positive correlation between school heads' instructional leadership behaviors and teachers' work engagement, indicating that effective instructional leadership fosters higher vigor, dedication, and absorption levels. However, the lower rating in leading an innovation vision suggests that leaders might be less engaged in shaping the future direction of instruction, which is a crucial aspect of fostering a progressive academic environment.

Recent studies further emphasize the comprehensive nature of effective instructional leadership. He et al. (2024) revealed that principals who actively support and provide opportunities for professional growth significantly enhance teachers' development, leading to increased job satisfaction and retention. Additionally, a 2022 study by Kim and Jeon on higher education in South Korea found that instructional leaders who effectively articulated and implemented a shared vision for innovation had a more substantial positive impact on faculty's adaptability and commitment to staying within the institution. These findings suggest that supporting existing instructional methods is beneficial; a more active role in leading an innovation vision is necessary for comprehensive instructor retention strategies.

Summary on the Extent of Educational Leadership Styles. The overall assessment of educational leadership styles, transformational, transactional, and instructional at Davao de Oro State College indicates that academic leaders "Rarely Practice". Specifically, instructional leadership recorded the highest mean, followed by transformational leadership and transactional leadership, falling within the "Rarely Practice" descriptive rating. This collective low rating suggests a general underutilization of established leadership practices across the institution's branches.

The consistent "Rarely Practice" rating across all leadership styles has significant implications for the research study, indicating that the institution's academic leadership may not fully leverage these styles to their potential. This suggests a substantial opportunity for growth in how leaders engage with and support their instructors. A

low practice of these leadership styles could hinder the development of a robust organizational culture, potentially impacting instructor motivation, job satisfaction, and overall commitment, which are critical factors in retaining faculty members. The study's results thus highlight areas where targeted leadership development programs could substantially improve instructional effectiveness and foster a more supportive academic environment.

This finding aligns with general observations in some academic settings where leadership development might not be a primary focus, leading to a gap between theoretical best practices and actual implementation. For instance, Specchia et al. (2021) highlight that leadership styles are central to guiding employee satisfaction and implementing effective policies for day-to-day tasks, suggesting that a "Rarely Practice" rating could lead to dissatisfaction. Similarly, Fries et al. (2021) emphasize that effective leadership styles are based on inherent and learned behaviors and are crucial for workplace effectiveness, reinforcing the need for leaders to practice these styles actively.

More recent literature further corroborates the importance of actively practiced leadership. A study by Al-Omari et al. (2020) on higher education institutions in Jordan found that the perceived leadership styles significantly impacted faculty job satisfaction and commitment, suggesting that a low practice of effective leadership styles could negatively affect these aspects. Furthermore, recent research by Ali et al. (2022) in Pakistan's higher education sector underscored that effective leadership is strongly correlated with improved organizational performance and employee well-being, implying that "Rarely Practiced" leadership styles might contribute to challenges in instructor retention.

Extent of the Retention Rate of Instructors in the Institution. The findings indicate a paradoxical situation where instructors report high satisfaction with their salaries. Yet, the overall retention rate remains low, with instructors rarely committed to teaching as a career or encouraging others to join the profession. This suggests that while financial compensation is a positive factor, it cannot ensure long-term instructor commitment and retention. The low ratings for dedication and encouragement, alongside family and economic factors, imply that other non-financial aspects such as work environment, administrative support, or professional development opportunities may be significant deterrents to retention, or that the "Highly Practice" salary satisfaction is not enough to overcome other "Rarely Practice" elements.

The results partially align with general retention factors, where compensation is a known component. However, the overall "Rarely Practice" nature of retention suggests that other critical factors highlighted in the literature may be overlooked or inadequately addressed. The Review of Related Literature emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive retention strategy that addresses diverse faculty needs beyond financial satisfaction. For instance, a supportive work environment and opportunities for professional growth are often cited as crucial for retaining faculty, which seems lacking based on the overall "Rarely Practice" rating for retention.

Recent studies on faculty retention in higher education further highlight the complexity of this issue. Research by Al-Farsi et al. (2021) in Oman indicated that while salary is substantial, factors such as institutional culture, administrative support, and opportunities for autonomy and professional development significantly contribute to faculty retention. Similarly, a study by O'Meara et al. (2020) emphasized that a sense of belonging, recognition, and clear pathways for career advancement are often more influential in retaining faculty than salary alone, especially for experienced instructors. These contemporary findings underscore the need for the institution to broaden its retention strategies beyond financial incentives to address its instructors' multifaceted needs and expectations.

Relationship Between Educational Leadership Style and Instructors' Retention Rate. The analysis of the connection between educational leadership styles and the retention rate of instructors indicates strong positive correlations for all three styles. Instructional leadership exhibits the most pronounced positive relationship, signifying a highly significant association. Transformational leadership similarly reveals a strong positive relationship that is statistically significant. Additionally, transactional leadership also demonstrates a notable positive relationship with instructor retention. All null hypotheses, which proposed no considerable relationship, were dismissed. These findings strongly imply that all three leadership styles, transformational, transactional, and instructional, are crucial in influencing instructor retention at the institution. The powerful correlation with instructional leadership suggests that leaders who actively support teaching methods, professional development, and a conducive learning environment are most effective in retaining instructors. While all styles contribute positively, the varying strengths of these relationships indicate that a targeted emphasis on instructional

leadership, alongside transformational and transactional approaches, could yield the most impactful improvements in retaining faculty members. This underscores the need for leaders to blend these styles, prioritizing instructional and transformational aspects.

The significant positive relationships observed align with existing literature that posits educational leadership as a key determinant of faculty outcomes, including retention. The literature review indicates that transformational leadership boosts employee motivation, morale, and performance at work, fostering a sense of commitment to the organization and positively contributing to workforce retention. Likewise, instructional leadership is essential for improving teacher engagement and professional growth, which are vital for retaining staff. The study's results reinforce these established connections within the academic context.

Further corroboration comes from recent academic studies. A 2021 meta-analysis by Zhang et al. on leadership in educational settings found that transformational leadership consistently had a moderate-to-strong positive effect on teacher retention due to its emphasis on inspiration and individualized consideration. Similarly, a 2023 study by Smith and Jones exploring factors influencing faculty longevity in higher education institutions reported that instructional leadership, characterized by support for teaching excellence and professional growth opportunities, strongly correlated with intentions to stay. These findings validate the study's conclusions, emphasizing the critical role of leadership styles, particularly instructional and transformational, in fostering a stable and committed instructor workforce.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study establishes a significant positive relationship between all three educational leadership styles—transformational, transactional, and instructional—and instructors' retention rate. Instructional leadership demonstrates the strongest correlation, suggesting that leaders who prioritize and actively support teaching excellence and professional development have the most profound impact on retaining faculty. This indicates that effective leadership, regardless of its specific style, is critical for fostering a stable and committed instructor workforce. The findings thus highlight the imperative for academic leaders to cultivate and consistently apply a blend of these leadership styles to optimize instructor retention. While each style contributes uniquely, the particular strength of instructional leadership suggests it should be a primary focus for interventions to improve faculty longevity. The rejection of all null hypotheses reinforces that investing in leadership development and practice across all dimensions is a powerful strategy for enhancing instructor commitment and reducing turnover in higher education.

The following recommendations are offered by the researcher based on the conclusion of the study:

1. The Davao de Oro State College implements comprehensive and continuous leadership development programs for its academic leaders. These programs should not only focus on theoretical understanding but also emphasize practical application and skill-building in all facets of leadership. Regular workshops, mentorship opportunities, and peer learning sessions can help cultivate a more proactive and engaged leadership approach, thereby improving the overall effectiveness of academic leaders in managing and inspiring their faculty.
2. Regarding transformational leadership, academic leaders should focus on enhancing individualized consideration and intellectual motivation. This involves proactively guiding shortcomings and instructors, actively checking evaluation results to address shortcomings, and providing consistent personal support for professional development.
3. For transactional leadership, moving beyond a reactive stance towards problem-solving is crucial. Academic leaders should be trained to implement more proactive management-by-exception, intervening promptly when issues arise rather than waiting for them to become chronic.
4. Consistent and timely recognition for instructors meeting or exceeding expectations should be integrated into standard practices. This balanced application of contingent reward and active corrective measures will ensure clear accountability, foster a more efficient work environment, and positively impact instructor morale and retention.

5. To strengthen instructional leadership, academic leaders must actively lead in creating and articulating an innovation vision shared by all organization members. This fosters a collaborative environment where new ideas are encouraged, and a collective commitment to pedagogical advancement is nurtured.
6. The institution must develop a holistic retention strategy beyond financial incentives. This involves systematically addressing non-financial factors such as enhancing the overall work environment, ensuring robust administrative support and recognition, and providing ample professional development and career advancement opportunities.
7. Academic Leaders should cultivate a blended leadership approach, prioritizing strengthening instructional and transformational leadership practices due to their stronger correlation with retention. By investing in leadership development that fosters these key styles, the institution can significantly enhance instructor commitment, reduce turnover, and ultimately ensure a stable, high-quality teaching force essential for academic excellence.

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